

SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Core-Shell Colloidal Nanocomposites for Local Temperature Monitoring During Photothermal Heating

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Summary of the Supporting Information Sections

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1. Synthesis of AuNR@SiO₂

Figure S1. High angle annular dark field scanning transmission electron microscopy (ADF-STEM) image of Au nanorods coated with mesoporous silica (AuNR@m-SiO₂, left) and TEM image of the same particles (right), where radially oriented pores can be observed. The scale bars represent 50 nm in both images.

2. Synthesis of Nd-doped LaOCl nanoparticles

Figure S2. A-F) TEM images of LaOCl:Nd nanoparticles synthesized with 60 (A), 30 (B) and 15 (C) minutes reaction time (scale bars are 100 nm) and corresponding size distributions (D-E-F). G) Photoluminescence spectrum of the 15 min sample excited with a 808 nm laser and band assignment. Transitions between Stark levels R1 and R2, and Z1...Z6 of the $^4F_{3/2}$ and $^4I_{11/2}$ manifold, respectively, suitable for intraband nanothermometry. H) Level diagram of the main Nd³⁺ emissions after absorption of 808 nm laser.

3. Synthesis of hybrid nanocomposites

Figure S3. A) Scheme of the synthetic process for the preparation of AuNR@mSiO₂-Nd nanocomposites. B) TEM images of AuNR@mSiO₂ and AuNR@mSiO₂-xNd nanoparticles, for the x-th synthetic steps (x = 1, 3, 8). C) Resulting size distributions for the long (red) and short (blue) AuNR axes. D) Size distribution of SiO₂ shell thickness. In panels C and D, the size distributions are referred to silica coated AuNRs, the intermediate products of the sequential synthesis, and the final nanocomposite.

4. Spectroscopic, structural, and morphological characterization

Figure S4. Photoluminescence spectra of NdNPs (black), AuNR@mSiO₂-NdNPs (grey) and chloroform (blue) under excitation at 808 nm.

Figure S5. High-resolution ADF-STEM image of the outer area of a nanocomposite, highlighting two LaOCl:Nd NPs on the silica surface, and Fast Fourier transform (FFT) patterns, matching a (010) orientation.

Figure S6. HAADF STEM images and elemental analysis for AuNR@mSiO₂ (A) and AuNR@mSiO₂-Nd nanoparticles (B), showing the distribution of Au, Si, and La from EDS measurements. EDS spectra are shown in the right panels.

Figure S7. A,B) Snapshots from a 3D visualization of the electron tomography reconstruction, showing the segmentation of LaOCl:Nd NPs within AuNR@mSiO₂-Nd nanocomposites. C) Orthoslice through the reconstructed volume, in which a slight penetration of LaOCl:Nd NPs inside the silica shell can be appreciated.

Figure S8. A,B) La 3d_{5/2} X-ray photoelectron spectra (XPS) of LaOCl:Nd NPs (A) and AuNR@SiO₂-LaOCl:Nd NPs (B), before (black dashed lines) and after (red dashed lines) sputtering. C,D) La 4p and Cl 2p XPS spectra of LaOCl:Nd NPs (C) and AuNR@SiO₂-LaOCl:Nd NPs (D), before (black dashed lines) and after (red dashed lines) sputtering.

5. Recalibration of B parameter

As demonstrated by Quintanilla *et al.*,¹ recalibration of the B parameter in Equations S1 and S2, must be performed *in situ*, otherwise a great uncertainty in the temperature sensing is expected. Following this procedure at $T = RT$, $\ln B$ can be expressed as follows,

$$\ln B = \ln \left(\frac{I_{ii}}{I_i} \right)_{RT} + \frac{\Delta E}{k_B RT} \quad [S1]$$

where all parameters are known except for that of LIR at RT: $(\ln I_{ii}/I_i)_{RT}$, which changes with B . This value can be estimated considering that it equals the value of the LIR when the laser is not illuminating the sample, *i.e.*, when the laser power P equals zero:

$$\ln \left(\frac{I_{ii}}{I_i} \right)_{RT} = \ln \left(\frac{I_{ii}}{I_i} \right)_{P=0} \quad [S2]$$

The LIR at $P = 0$ is the intercept of the linear fit performed on the experimental values of the LIR, obtained by varying the laser power, as displayed in **Figure 5B**. At this point, $\ln B$ is known and the temperature T can be explicitly determined from Equation S2.

$$T = \frac{\Delta E/k_B}{\ln B - \ln LIR} \quad [S3]$$

6. Nanocomposite stability – PL through time

Figure S9.- Photoluminescence intensity before and after irradiation experiments on the same sample, under different laser power densities. The irradiation time between the initial and the final spectrum for each power density (pairs with the same color) was 5 minutes.

References

1. Quintanilla, M.; Henriksen-Lacey, M.; Renero-Lecuna C.; Liz-Marzán, L. M. Challenges for Optical Nanothermometry in Biological Environments. *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2022**, *51*, 4223–4242.